

Arguments for the Bajan Creole, the Spanish Portuguese Perspective

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For: Barbados Community College

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“Creolization is a key concept in studies of cultural change in colonial conditions. Most typically, it refers to a mode of cultural transformation undertaken by people from different cultural groups who converge in a colonial territory to which they have not previously belonged. This was especially pronounced in the slave plantation economies of the Caribbean basin, where the indigenous peoples were largely wiped out or deported during colonization and the societies that replaced them were largely developed from the intermixture of transplanted Europeans and enslaved Africans. Creolization has been theorized in many different ways by scholars in disciplines across the humanities and social sciences.” 11

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Creolisation occurs in pluralistic societies, where many individuals of different places and ethnicities settle in small islands and become committed to their new reality, rather than being conceptualised through the mainlands of Colonial Empires, such as England, Iberia, the Ottoman Empire, and elsewhere.

Through this process, different ethnicities and cultures form societies that reflect the historical influences and dynamics of their time period, rather than strictly what a colonial regime, or set of laws, would imply they should do.

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inferior and derivative, rather than seeking to learn what these statements map onto paper phonetically. Anglicization erases linguistic origins (Iberian, African, Asians, Irish) by forcing English ‘respectable’ spelling/interpretation. Think of the contrast of writing does instead of duz, does is the incorrect form of English which is not tolerated upon official paper, duz is Bajan, it sounds like the world we speak without the additional lair of imposed Colonial English norms. Iberianization on the contrary restores those erased possibilities by situating Bajan in a multilingual, multiethnic late 17th-century Barbadian contact zone.

Neutral Bajan interprets Bajan words through an interpretative lens, not necessarily English, but factoring in what these terms mean in the local context, what they sound like, and where they draw similarities from, or sound similar. For the purposes of this study, my interpretative lens is not Neutral, but Iberian. I am using my neutral lens of Barbadian creole, and analysing the subject matter most pertinent to the Iberian contribution to the creolisation of Bajan into what it is today. This is not to argue Bajan is Portuguese. But to say Iberianization is a corrective lens, one that restores overlooked Iberian contributions, balancing against over-Anglicization..... 31

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man → [mã]

down → [dõũ] ~ [dõun]

Nasal vowels are frequent, especially in rapid or emphatic speech.

Portuguese:

mão [mãw̃] (hand), bom [bõ], pão [pãw̃].

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Iberianized Bajan: de = Of (e.g., 'Bring mi de ting') / Dey = there (E.g 'Da dey') / Duz = To do something (e.g 'Dah duz pull') / E (He, or abstract for a person).....	39

Introduction

This essay argues that Barbadian Creole bears an additional, understudied Iberian layer, particularly Judaeo-Portuguese, visible in definite-marking strategies (de/da), prepositional stacking, prosody, and proverb structure. While Bajan's grammar is fundamentally depicted as an English-lexifier creole, Sephardic contact in 17th-century Bridgetown/Speightstown likely reinforced or contributed to specific function-word patterns already emerging in the island's multilingual contact ecology.

This essay thus argues that Barbadian Creole **may carry** traces of Judeo-Portuguese-influenced phonetic speech, brought by Sephardic Jews fleeing Iberia, which have been overlooked by dominant Anglo-African centric narratives of creole formation within the British Empire. The Judaeo-Portuguese and Afro-Portuguese dimensions of Barbadian life are an additional layer in context to British and African norms, not an erasure of them.

For clarity, I've placed a glossary of technical terms at the end, so you can refer to it if required.

Methodology

This article employs a comparative-historical and ethnolinguistic approach, supported by archival analysis and contextualized through a decolonial minoritarian perspective. The methodology employed is designed to integrate linguistic evidence, historical documentation, and cultural memory to recover Iberian contributions to Barbadian Creole.

Comparative-Historical Linguistics

Core features of Bajan Creole (de, mi, en, wuh) are examined alongside cognates in modern Portuguese, Old Galician-Portuguese, and Judeo-Portuguese. The analysis focuses on syntax (e.g., prepositional stacking, article usage), morphology (negation and pronoun forms), and phonology (vowel reduction, syllable shortening). This comparative framework highlights structural parallels that suggest Iberian influence in the formative stages of Barbadian Creole.

Archival-Historical Contextualization

Seventeenth-century census records, synagogue archives, wills, and gravestone inscriptions are employed to situate Judaeo-Portuguese speakers in Barbados. Families of Portuguese Sephardic origin, including the Baruch Lousadas (Barrows), De Silvas, Dellyons, and Massiahs, are documented in Bridgetown and Speightstown during the period when Barbadian Creole was emerging. These sources provide the historical foundation for linking linguistic survivals to documented Sephardic communities, and they mention artifacts that were left behind, such as wills, which were in Portuguese or Hebrew—Which might have been Judaeo-Portuguese in Rashi Script.

Ethnolinguistic Use of Oral Tradition

Barbadian proverbs and idiomatic expressions are treated as legitimate linguistic archives. Structures such as *De higher de monkey climb, de more he show he tail* are compared with Iberian parallels, notably the repetition of prepositions (*de...de...*) in Judeo-Portuguese and Ladino proverbial forms. This ethnolinguistic lens positions oral speech and cultural memory as evidence on par with written texts, revealing survivals overlooked by archival bias.

Decolonial Framework

The analysis is explicitly situated within a decolonial framework that challenges Anglo-African or Americanized models of multicultural Creolization, which marginalize Iberian and Jewish contributions within Barbadian sociolinguistic history. In addition, this decolonial framework employed aligns Barbados' sociopolitical development closer with that of Latin America than Europe or North America. The decolonial perspective finds that, provided critical analysis, dynamics in context to language, race, colonialism, and colonization are better explored from the positionality of our geographical proximity and similar histories.

By foregrounding archival silences, Anglicization, and respectability politics, the study interprets linguistic survivals not as accidental residues but as evidence of systematic erasure and resistance in a manner that speaks to the British Caribbean, from the perspective of an Iberian minority community. The decolonial lens also recognizes the role of Sephardic Jews as both colonizers and colonized, complicating simplistic binaries of power and identity in the Caribbean.

Researcher Positionality

As a Barbadian of Portuguese Sephardic descent, I acknowledge my dual role as both researcher and descendant. I speak through this connection to my mother, and my father, through Martin Luther Barrow, Merle Mary Shirley Springer, and Lance Neville King II. This positionality informs the study's focus on erasure and recovery, shaping

the interpretive lens through which Iberian survivals are read, in a creole and inclusive light. While the analysis is grounded in comparative and archival methods, it is also guided by an awareness that knowledge production is entangled with identity and memory.

The perception of Jews within Iberian Imagination,

In 1637, Diego de Cisneros, a cleric and jurist living in Rouen, France, wrote to King Philip IV of Spain. His missive, which spans almost thirty pages, deals with an issue of utmost concern to the expatriate clergyman: the worldwide threat posed by what he calls New Jews, by which he means baptized Christians of Portuguese Jewish descent who retained an affinity for or commitment to Judaism. He writes: “With horrific cruelty and evil-doing, the Jews have continued their persecution in all the provinces of the world, provoking Christians to a common defense, uniting all the nations of the faithful against the perfidious nation of the Jews.”

This anxiety reflected an increasing awareness of the presence of the people of *la Nação* “the Nation,” at the center of political and economic life throughout the Iberian empires. Yet that awareness carried with it a perception of risk that Portuguese Conversos were also a people with an intertwined and inherently dangerous political, economic, and religious identity—one that threatened the divine favor bestowed on the combined Spanish and Portuguese empires.

I contend that as the combined Spanish and Portuguese empires drifted toward crisis in the 1630s and 1640s, many individuals identified Portuguese conversos the people of “the Nation” whose trading networks reached to the edge of the empires—as a global infection that was a primary source of that crisis; and many found the remedy to this infection in a similarly global institution: the various tribunals of the Spanish and Portuguese Inquisitions. —

Starr-LeBeau, G. (2021). A Global “Infection” of Judaizing: Investigations of Portuguese New Jews and New Christians in the 1630s and 1640s. Interfaith Relationships and Perceptions of the Other in the Medieval Mediterranean. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-83997-0_7

Portuguese Jews were culturally liminal and marginalised figures who oftentimes were met special challenges, such as legal marginalisation and armed resistance wherever they had gone, often in juxtaposition to Christian piety, Economic factors, minority status and respectability politics; thus, we can see a cultural incentive as to why the language of the nation would be seen as lesser, especially by the Anglican planter elite, which compromised primarily of Anglican, colonial ‘aristocratic’ British elites, in juxtaposition to the indentured, and enslaved means of speech that would come to influence the Creolization of multiple creole states into what is now, modern Bajan creole, an English font with Iberian influences, which is not standardised and shifts between American, and British linguistic influences.

It is additionally notable due to the shifting colonial powers of Jamaica, its patwa has developed more distinctly,

and pronounced toward the creolized phonetic speech of African, Iberian, and Anglo-Influence, as is the case for Haiti, but wearing a French font. Creolization is an inevitable part of Small Island reconstituted communities. For one such reason, decolonial scholarship must discuss factual and inclusive ethnoreligious ancestry, juxtaposed to widely parroted narratives, which are formed by very few academic elites.

In different Caribbean territories, we see this ‘creole tongue’ and legacy manifested differently, such as in Suriname, Curaçao, Haiti, and other regions of reconstituted Eura-African Island life. Some Caribbean languages lean more toward Indian influences in locations where there was more migration from individuals of South-Asian origin, but even in such contexts, it is notable to mention that the process of creolisation does not reach a permanent state or evolution.

Definitions, Creolization

“Creolization is a key concept in studies of cultural change in colonial conditions. Most typically, it refers to a mode of cultural transformation undertaken by people from different cultural groups who converge in a colonial territory to which they have not previously belonged. This was especially pronounced in the slave plantation economies of the Caribbean basin, where the indigenous peoples were largely wiped out or deported during colonization and the societies that replaced them were largely developed from the intermixture of transplanted Europeans and enslaved Africans. Creolization has been theorized in many different ways by scholars in disciplines across the humanities and social sciences.”

Creole Language,

‘Creole language (krēōl’), any language that began as a pidgin but was later adopted as the mother tongue by a people in place of the original mother tongue or tongues. Examples are the Gullah of South Carolina and Georgia (based on English), the creole of Haiti (based on French), and the Papiamentu of the Netherlands possessions in the West Indies (developed from pidgin Spanish and Portuguese). Similarities among creoles worldwide have led some linguists to speculate that they share a common origin, probably Sabir (see lingua franca); others attribute the similarities to universal laws governing human language.’ — **"creole language ."** **The Columbia Encyclopedia, 6th ed.. . Retrieved September 03, 2025 from Encyclopedia.com:**

<https://www.encyclopedia.com/reference/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/creole-language>

Creole tongues within the linguistic context of Anglo-dominated Barbados are to be understood in an Anglicized context, where the main linguistic element of society was the imposition of British, Christian Colonialism.

The Method of Creolisation,

Creolisation occurs in pluralistic societies, where many individuals of different places and ethnicities settle in small islands and become committed to their new reality, rather than being conceptualised through the mainlands of Colonial Empires, such as England, Iberia, the Ottoman Empire, and elsewhere.

Through this process, different ethnicities and cultures form societies that reflect the historical influences and dynamics of their time period, rather than strictly what a colonial regime, or set of laws, would imply they should do. For example, Christian slaves were forbidden in many regions, in some contexts, but that did not stop African Christians, who were baptised and forced into Christianity, from being owned regardless of legislative technicality within the British Empire.

Barbadian Jews, of Sephardic, Portuguese Origin, were part of a contested form of living, rights could be given or

taken on a whim, the threat of violence was currency, as was slavery brutal, and barbaric, the ‘human rights’ record of the British Regime toward its Jewish people was not stain free, in 1290, through Edward I, England expelled its Jews. This leads to a contested record where the British Regime is perceived as ambivalent to Jews, but in its function, behaved as equally hostile toward them as it had its Irish denizens.

The Jews and Irish shared similar positionality, both transplanted ‘European’ diasporas who were marginalized within the British Empire. Barbadian Jews were juxtaposed to the rights of the Poor Whites when it came time for Catholic, Jewish, and African emancipation, each category having its own ethnicities and groupings within them.

This is documented in ‘Making Jews’ by Laura A. Leibman, discussing Jewish emancipation in context to Jewish identity, within Colonial Barbados.

Definitions, Bajan

Dialect of Barbados

What Is Bajan Dialect?

During informal settings, British English is both the spoken and written official language of Barbados; more casual settings see Barbadians speak a unique dialect like no other.

The local language of Barbados is often referred to as the Bajan dialect or “Bajan.”

Bajan dialect is a slang version of standard English, or simplified pidgin English, mixed with unique 'Bajanisms' unique to the island. Barbadians speak with an accent best described as a combination of the influences of both African and British languages.

Bajans speak in their native dialect using colorful, expressive, fast-paced words. The Bajan dialect can be tricky to follow at times, especially for visitors to the island. To add to this, each individual speaks their personalized version of the dialect, and new words and expressions are added continuously and accepted as part of the everyday vocabulary of Barbados. Callaghan, B. (2024, August 14). Dialect of Barbados. Totally Barbados. <https://www.totallybarbados.com/articles/culture/dialect/>

Discussing the matter of 'Barbadian Creole'

'There has been much debate, pro and con, as to whether contemporary Barbadian nonstandard English, popularly known as 'Bajan,' had a true basilectal creole in its history and went through the classical pidgin-creole-decreolization cycle to arrive at its present mesolectal status. The reason why this debate seems not to be an easy one to resolve is that the sociohistorical situation in Barbados in the early years of its history was not as straightforward and clearcut as in most other English-speaking Caribbean islands. The situation was similar enough, in general terms, to other islands to expect that the same linguistic outcome could ensue, but it was also different enough in certain details to support some variation in this regard.' — Arends, J. (ed. . (1995). **The Early Stages of Creolization (Vol. 00013). John Benjamins Publishing Company.**

In the Barbadian Creole, there are statements that we commonly make that are not contextualized within an Iberian perspective. Most emblematic of this is the usage of the preposition ‘de’, as in ‘Bring mi de ting, nuh’. Within Iberian and Lusophone tongues, ‘de’ is a preposition which means of, or from; however, within the Barbadian Sociolinguistic context, it means ‘The’.

We find statements and phrases that contain ‘mi’, a Spanish and Ladino-influenced form of saying ‘me’ or ‘I’, contextualised within an Afro-English pidgin paradigm, rather than parsing the influence of Spanish, Portuguese, and other communities within these regions. For this reason, it is deemed pertinent to analyze and discuss what some of these terms read as, from another linguistic perspective.

The three prepositions in the Bajan linguistic syntax ‘de, da’, and das’ provide us insight into earlier states of the Barbadian Creole, which were spoken. This may explain why regions within Barbados that are considered the countryside often have a much more pronounced Barbadian Linguistic profile than others. Within Old Galician Portuguese, de was a catch-all preposition; it had many contractions with definite articles, such as o, a, os, and as, like within modern Portuguese, which is how we reach ‘na, nos, do, dos, da, das’.

It is noted that multiple prepositions had often been employed, similarly to how older forms of Spanish, as influenced in preserved forms of Ladino. Old Galician Portuguese serves as a cultural basis for the spoken language of the Barbadian Spanish-Portuguese because these Jews had been Iberian exiles, fleeing refugees, and descendants of Anusim who flowed through Portuguese diasporic networks, but were disconnected from Portugal itself due to the looming threat of inquisitors. These Jews brought with them many languages; they had comprised a group of Portuguese Jews from all over the world, as documented in the discussion concerning the Speightstown Jews.

‘We know by this date the Nidhe Israel Synagogue in Bridgetown had been functioning for sometime, this excerpt suggests another synagogue was operative in another part of the island by this date, as does the following excerpt from a pamphlet by Quaker leader George Fox written in 1686 to attempt to convert the Jews of Barbados:

Lichtenstein (2018) documents that by 1680 at least seventy Sephardim lived in Speightstown, organized around merchants like Joseph Mendes, who left a Portuguese codicil in his 1707 will. Additionally, it shows that individuals named Barrow, Massiah, Da Silva, Mendes, and many other combinations were known to be active, practicing Sephardic Jews of Primarily Portuguese Origins — **Lichtenstein, Rachel (2018)The Lost Synagogue of Speightstown: New Findings in the Light of Recent Investigations. Journal of the Barbados Museum and Historical Society, LXIV (85th A). pp. 196-226. ISSN 0005-5891**

Continuing the discussion of the influence of Portuguese on the modern Creole, particularly a diasporic and fluid form of Jewish language from Jewish families, it is integral to note the survival of cultural influences, juxtaposed with imposed language. A notable aspect of the Bajan creole is the shortening of words, or statements, in statements such as ‘Wa Hppn’, phonetically which may sound akin to ‘W’hahpun?’ as substituted for ‘what happened’ and ‘wa gine on’ for ‘What is going on’; the aspect of reduced vowels in Portuguese Syntax shares similarities to this linguistic inheritance.

When we observe the shifting of *de* from an all-purpose preposition to a definite article replacing ‘A’ and ‘O’ in Portuguese as a linguistic progression from an older stage of Barbados, which had not been fully anglicized, to a remnant of Iberian speech in a Creolized context. This progression could have occurred due to linguistic similarities and reinforcement within other Island creoles, once more, exemplifying the Creolization of language in Barbados. Presently, many Sephardic descendants understand, speak, and are capable of writing Bajan, but others are not. Barbadian Creole is not monolithic.

Notably, the Bajan **de** used as a definite marker is widely analyzed and presented as an internal creole development from English **the/that**; here I argue that Iberian contact likely **contributed to** this pattern within Barbados, especially in fixed proverbial frames and prepositional stacking. We must also not forget that the Africans brought to Barbados were not a monolithic group of people; they themselves brought different languages and dialects. They had often passed through Spanish, Portuguese, or otherwise networks during the scramble for Africa, and the mass

proliferation of slavery, several generations of identity existed upon the brutal reality of torture at sea, and torture on land.

Reduced Vowels

This is what people are referring to when they say that European Portuguese speakers like to “eat” or “swallow” their vowels! Reduced vowels are basically vowels that are unstressed to the point that they are barely pronounced or even dropped entirely.

For example, the sounds for o and e are typically reduced in unstressed syllables at the end of a word. Listen to how the final o’s and e’s in *ralado*, *isso*, *disse*, etc. are pronounced in these sentences:

E eu ralado com isso
I couldn't care less (idiom)

Foi aquele tipo que me disse isso.
It was that guy (slang) who told me that

This is because European Portuguese is a stress-timed language, which means that the stressed syllables are pronounced very strongly and the unstressed syllables are shortened. In other words, more time is given to the

stressed syllables.

Brazilian Portuguese, on the other hand, displays both stress-timed and syllable-timed properties, depending on the dialect, rate of speech, length of a phrase, and other contextual factors. In general, however, it tends to be more syllable-timed compared to European Portuguese. – **Practice Portuguese. (n.d.). Pronunciation guide for European Portuguese vowels. Retrieved September 20, 2025, from <https://www.practiceportuguese.com/learning-notes/pronunciation-guide-for-european-portuguese-vowels/>**

We do see evidence of vowel shortening within the Barbadian Creole, as stated prior, ‘what’ becomes ‘wuh’ in spoken tongue when in dialogue with another statement, wa often serves as a stacked interrogative, innately a question, but delivered sharply and quickly, similarly, a statement like ‘what has happened’ becomes phonetically similar ‘hppn?’ which can be abrupt, and contextualized for non-speakers of the creole.

In Portuguese, phrases become shorter in spoken practice rather than writing; this enables fluid communication, but reflects phonetic influences conflicting with standardised language. For this reason, this sort of speech carries more cultural legitimacy, as it reflects the lived reality of the Portuguese culture in that diaspora, which often develops in context with local populations, a diverse mixture of peoples from across the world, some indentured and enslaved, some plantation elites, and others.

Naming Traditions

The duplication of names across generations, often accompanied by an anglicized lastname which typically appears as being of British origin, we find that Sephardic Gravestones, and families often repeat the same names across generations, this creates archival confusion and duplications that often collapse multiple generations into a single person, however this occurs primarily because of Anglicized bureaucracies which favored names which were understandable within a British environment, rather than an Iberian inflected naming system. It is widely acknowledged that the Bajan linguistic context was formed in context to Anglican assimilation, which forms the basis for the Bajan creole being understood as a dialect or ‘degraded’ formulation of English, although—in truth, what survives within our neglected linguistic imprint serves boons in understanding the creolised inheritance Barbadians claim as their own.

Internally, as elders would pass through communities, the same name might have gotten confused across generations, even though there might have been a hidden subtlety that an archive might neglect, such as middle names. In some rare cases, Iberian descendants, particularly males, inherited the exact name as their fathers.

Whereas names such as Maria, Mary, Rebecca, Ann, Lucia, Luceta, or many other ‘ambiguous’ names appear. Within an Anglophone, these names may not seem significant; they may even feel ‘elitist’ or ‘foreign’ — but they

are ultimately traceable across Sephardic diasporas. This implies the linguistic origin of these names still appears culturally, even if they are sometimes illegible due to a lack of cultural sensitivity or archival sensibility.

Many Iberians understand how their names, particularly those that serve to identify lineage, remain an integral part of their heritage. However, archival sources in Barbados omit these integral details, which reflects poor archival practices, rather than a lack of continuity. Oftentimes, when these names do appear and are detailed in full, there may be archival errors that lead to the shifting of names among family groups. Different jurisdictions and bureaucratic clerks had diverse motivations, skills, and connections at their disposal.

Discussing Judaeo-Portugues and La Nação

Judeo-Portuguese, History

The Jewish Languages Project explains that Judeo-Portuguese, spoken widely by the *Nação Portuguesa*, functioned as a diasporic lingua franca across Europe and the Caribbean before declining after the 18th century.

‘Little research has been done on the linguistic features of Emigré Judeo-Portuguese. According to Germano's (1968) study of texts from Amsterdam and Hamburg between the eighteenth and twentieth centuries, the Jewish variety included more archaic forms than the standard Portuguese of that time. The Portuguese linguist B.N. Teesma (1975) calls the eighteenth-century language of Mendes-Franco (1772) a "fossilized Portuguese" and

an "Ibero-Galic-Dutch hodge-podge." Mendes-Franco's text, written in Latin letters, includes numerous Hebrew loanwords, mostly from the semantic fields of Jewish tradition and community life. The Hebrew words appear either in Hebrew characters or in transliteration.’ — **Sharon, M. (n.d.). Judeo-Portuguese. In Jewish Language Project. Sarah Bunin Benor (Ed.). Retrieved September 20, 2025, from <https://www.jewishlanguages.org/judeo-portuguese>**

‘Many of the Jews expelled from Spain in 1492 sailed to seek refuge in other Mediterranean lands. A group estimated at 50–100,000 crossed the frontier into Portugal where they joined a Jewish community that has been established for several centuries.

The breathing space they secured for themselves did not last long. In 1496, the Portuguese King Manuel I issued an order for their expulsion. However, when he realized the serious economic implications, the king decided to keep them in the country – as Christians. He ordered that all Jews up to the age of 21 be forcibly baptized, in the hope that this would stop their parents from leaving. When 20,000 Jews did gather in Lisbon to sail away from the country, he had them baptized by force and declared citizens of his kingdom.

Only a very few submitted to baptism willingly. In most cases, the Jews were dragged to the font, but continued to observe Judaism privately. At first their secret Jewish observance was much easier to maintain than under similar circumstances in Spain, as the Inquisition was not introduced into Portugal until the mid-16th century.

Whenever the opportunity to escape from the country presented itself, these "New Christians" left. They traveled far and wide in search of non-Catholic lands where they could cast off their adopted faith and resume their Jewish identity.' – **American-Israeli Cooperative Enterprise. (n.d.). *Spanish-Portuguese Nation of the Caribbeans: La Nación. Jewish Virtual Library.* Retrieved September 20, 2025, from <https://www.jewishvirtuallibrary.org/la-nacion> [jewishvirtuallibrary.org](https://www.jewishvirtuallibrary.org)**

The *Jewish Virtual Library* (n.d.) recounts that Portuguese Jews, forced into baptism in 1497, later fled to colonies such as Barbados, where by 1679 the community numbered about 300.

Cultural evidence of Spanish-Portuguese expression

We do know, as evidenced by the graves of Spanish-Portuguese Jews at the Nidhe Israel, that they spoke Portuguese, Spanish, and retained what would appear as Hebrew as a liturgical and communal language, some, as referenced before wrote documents within Portuguese, rather than English, as evidenced, 'The most prominent member of the community was a wealthy merchant called 'Joseph Mendes of Speights a considerable landowner' who Samuel believed was the founder of the Speightstown Synagogue, information which he probably gleaned from the Portuguese codicil of Joseph Mendes will dated 17 July 1707 in which Joseph Mendes leaves 'my 3rd part which I have in the holy synagogue called Snead (? Semah) David consecrated to the Poor.'

And ‘The two Hebrew printed papers were delivered to the Jews at their two synagogues...at the one they were indifferent at the other they were not.’ Official records of the Speightstown Jewish community start in 1679 when the Governor of the island Jonathan Atkins, after an appeal from the Board of Trade Plantations, conducted the first census on the island.’ — **Lichtenstein, Rachel (2018)The Lost Synagogue of Speightstown: New Findings in the Light of Recent Investigations. Journal of the Barbados Museum and Historical Society, LXIV (85th A). pp. 196-226. ISSN 0005-5891**

However, I argue that the language these Hebrews spoke, and left a legacy of, was closer to Judaeo-Portuguese and Ladino as recognized today, than modern Hebrew or Modern Portuguese. I further suggest that it would have been impossible for these Spanish-Portuguese Jews to speak Modern Hebrew as represented by the state of Israel, as it had not been invented yet.

Barbadian Sephardic Gravestone Epitaphs:

Sarah Leah de Campos Pereira

‘Asusena desojada

Y tu fragança perdida

Mas tu olor es permanente

En la Eterna Vida

*A drooping lily
With its lost fragrance
But your perfume will last forever
In Eternal Life'*
—**Sarah Leah de Campos Pereira, 1736**

Rachel Lopez
*Mortal que de un tumba te devías
Sin reparar que es tu vida un viento
Mira que muerte cruel y Tirana
Sino vinere oy vendra mañana.*

*Mortal, you who from this tomb steps aside
Without regard to the fact that your life is but the wind,
Look on this cruel and tyrannical death
Which has come or will come tomorrow.*
—**Rachel Lopez, 1723**

‘SEPULTURA DO BEM AVENTURADO
DO DAVID RAPHAEL DE MERCADO
QUE FALECEO EM 2 DE MENACHEM

6344. SUA ALMA GOZE DA GLORIA’

— **David Raphael de Mercado**

Tomb of the Blessed

David Raphael de Mercado

Who died on the 2nd of Menachem [Av]

6344. May his soul enjoy glory.

‘The earliest epitaphs in the cemetery were written in Hebrew and Portuguese.

English started appearing in the 18th century and was predominant in the 19th and 20th centuries.

Often the occupation of the deceased was mentioned: merchant, trader, doctor, rabbi, hazan, warden.

*In the late 18th century, with the Enlightenment and subsequent Romanticist influences, epitaphs became commemorative odes, love poems and even warnings to visitors.’ — **Reading the Epitaphs as You Pass By** —*

Nidhe Israel Museum Guide

What we in fact have recorded are Judaeo-Lingustic fragments represented by the unique languages of Jewish communities in diaspora, for example, Judaeo-Portuguese has retained the Rashi alphabet for many of its preserved terms, in the same manner as Ladino. Some examples are:

Roš hašaná — Jewish New Year — ראש השנה

šabá — Shabbat — שבת

Micvá — Mitzvah, Commandments — מצוה

kadoš — Holy — קדוש

O Livro De Magica — The Book of Magic — או ליברו די מגיקה

algũa — Any — alguma — אלגומה

angora — Now — אנגורה

hũa — One — הוא

Linguistic Analysis:

Bajan Creole: *De man come hay.* — (“The man came here.”)

Portuguese: *O homem veio aqui.* / contraction: *do homem* = “of the man”

Papiamentu: *E homber a bin aki.* ‘A man come here’

Judaeo-Portuguese: ‘*La Homen veyo aki*’ ‘*O Homen veyo aki*’ ‘**ome veyo aki.**’ —

‘*Del homen*’ or ‘*Do homen*’ — ‘Of the man’ documents show heavy use of *de* and stacked prepositions (*de, do, de la*), similar to Ladino (Judezmo), Spanish words were common with Judaeo-Portuguese, exemplifying linguistic fluidity within the root language itself.

Bajan Creole with negation: *Bring me de ting, nuh.*

European Portuguese, enclisis: *Traz-me a coisa.*

European Portuguese proclisis with negation: *Não me tragas a coisa.*

Brazilian Portuguese proclisis with negation: *Não me traga a coisa.*

Cape Verdean with Negation Creole: *Ka traze-m kuza.*

Early modern Portuguese favored enclisis (Traz-me), which aligns typologically with clitic-after-verb placement in other Iberian languages of the period.

Negation and clitics

In Bajan, negation often surfaces as en (“I en do dat”). Mainstream analyses derive en from English ain’t/ent; I adopt this as the baseline and test whether Iberian contact reinforced its distribution. In Portuguese, não negates the clause and triggers proclisis (Não me tragas a coisa), whereas affirmative imperatives favor enclisis (Traz-me a coisa).

The Barbadian Creole does not lack clitic morphology; the frequent placement of object pronouns adjacent to the verb (“Bring me de ting”) typologically aligns with Iberian tendencies for high-frequency function words to cluster near the verb. In other sentences, we see clitic morphology, which will be addressed below. I interpret this as consistent with typological parallels found in Iberian languages, possibly reinforced by contact between languages.

Notice on Methodology:

While there have been no written attempts to standardize Bajan at an academic level, there have been several postings or communal endeavors to bring Bajan Creole into written form. For these purposes, I have seen that our language, Bajan, is often Americanized or Anglicized. For example most writers of Bajan would write ‘does’ instead of ‘duz’ or ‘ain’ instead of ‘en’, this reflects the difference between how linguistics is written, as opposed to how it is spoken.

I identify the tendency for Barbadians to model their speech on Imperial models of English be it Americanized or Anglicized to be at outcome of the colonised adopting the coloniser's tongue as common, and standard. Thus, I seek in this work to express Bajan words in the manner which they are phonetically spoken. This may make my analysis of the Bajan tongue controversial, but it must also exemplify how much of our true tongue is suppressed by Anglican, English dominance.

Anglicized Bajan vs Neutral Bajan

Anglicized Bajan interpretes Bajan words through an english colonial lense, so as to say, what does this phonetic combination sound like in English. Anglicized Bajan, like English, will always translate bajan terms in a purified anglicized manner that is held in juxtaposition to English, inferior and derivative, rather than seeking to learn what these statements map onto paper phonetically. Anglicization erases linguistic origins (Iberian, African, Asians, Irish) by forcing ‘respectable’ English spelling/interpretation. Think of the contrast of writing does instead of duz, does is the incorrect form of english which is not tolerated upon official paper, duz is Bajan, it sounds like the word we speak without the additional layer of imposed Colonial English norms. Iberianization on the contrary restores those erased possibilities by situating Bajan in a multilingual, multiethnic late 17th-century Barbadian contact zone.

Neutral Bajan interprets bajan words through an interpretative lens, not necessarily english, but factoring in what these terms mean in the local context, what they sound like, and where they draw similarities from, or sound similar. For the purposes of this study, my interpretative lens is not Neutral, but Iberian. I am using my neutral lens of Barbadian creole, and analysing the subjectmatter most pertinent to the Iberian contribution to the creolisation of Bajan into what it is today. This is not to argue Bajan is Portuguese. But to say Iberianization is a corrective lens, one that restores overlooked Iberian contributions, balancing against over-Anglicization.

Examples –

Phonetic Bajan Creole = **Yuh duz do dah?**

Anglicized Bajan = “**You does do that?**” (broken English)

Iberianized Bajan Creole = “**You duz (habitually) do that?**” (habitual marker like Portuguese *costumar*)

Shows Iberian-style aspect marking

Phonetic Bajan Creole = **Bring mi de ting**

Anglicized Bajan = “**Bring me the thing**” (English definite article)

Iberianized Bajan = “**Bring me of the thing**” (*de* as Iberian prepositional article)

Iberian stacking preserved

Phonetic Bajan Creole: **Dah** dey

Anglicized Bajan Creole = “**That is there**” (English demonstrative)

Iberianized Bajan Creole = “**Of that, there**” (**dah** = da = de + ah = da + **stress**)

Links to Portuguese contraction

What does ‘A’ mean in Barbadian? ‘A’ can be interpreted as ‘Ah’ such as in ‘Ah en got na money’
It serves as a preposition signifying the self, ‘Ah cyn unnstan?’ something like ‘I’, when this sound ‘ah’ is
combined with ‘de’ it becomes ‘da’ or when stressed ‘**dah**’ which becomes ‘that’

An example of Portuguese clitics

O João viu -me.

the John saw-me

"John saw me."

An example of Bajan Clitics

'Da John dah-see me?'

'That's John that saw me?' – English

'From the (feminine) John from the (dah meaning stressed 'that' which is typically stressed before words, it may also sound like 'dat', but is not to be confused with 'daz' or 'das' which functions more as 'that is') saw me' —

Creole read in Portuguese

Like in English, the Creole can be said to 'speak' the language improperly as it combines a feminine plural with a masculine singular, whereas 'de' in the English-Pidgin perspective appears to be a malformation of 'the'. I believe this reflects, rather than the explicit origin of this thread being English pidgin in Barbados, a part of a wider narrative of Barbadian linguistic Creolization. For that purpose, it is important to mention:

The prior statement in the Bajan Creole would be better translated to;
‘Dah’wan’John see-muh’ – An example of Barbadian Creole Clitic Morphology

‘That one John saw me.’

Bajan Creole: I en du dah. (“I didn’t do that.”)

Portuguese: Eu não fiz isso.

Judeo-Portuguese: Éu ãno fiz eso.

Cape Verdean Creole: N ka fazi es.

The Bajan Creole resembles the Iberian ‘en’, but can be spoken with a more Americanized inflection that sounds akin to ‘ain’; however, ‘in’, shortened ‘did-en’ exemplifies linguistic shortening. I must note that I resist the Americanization of the Barbadian language, and I therefore do not find Americanized standardizations such as ‘ain’t’, which I see as foreign to the Barbadian context.

Bajans typically say ‘Du’ instead of ‘Do’, however this depends on region.

*In Portuguese, **no** is the contraction **em + o** (‘in the’), with parallels **na** (em+a), **do/dos/da/das** (de+article). The term meaning ‘no’ came from the Latin *nōn*, which evolved into *non*, which had variant spellings, such as *eno* and *ẽno*. In modern Portuguese, this evolved into *não*, in Barbadian Creole, the term ‘en’, which may draw its roots from the Iberian ‘en, em’ as in ‘in’, or it might have been from the Judaeo Portuguese ‘Eno’ or its variants.*

This linguistic survival finds support in archival traces concerning what we know of the Portuguese of early Sephardic gravestones. We see terms such as 'Fillo' and 'Filla' representing a more archaic Portuguese origin constituent with other norms for that time period, such as fijo rather than the mother 'Filho' or 'hijo'. Ultimately, the cultural linguistic identity of Iberian languages and their influence diminished over time.

Portuguese Comparative Analysis

Nasalization

Bajan Creole:

man → [mã]

down → [dõõ] ~ [dõon]

Nasal vowels are frequent, especially in rapid or emphatic speech.

Portuguese:

mão [mãw̃] (hand), *bom* [bõ], *pão* [pãw̃].

Nasalization is a hallmark of Portuguese phonology, although it is less pronounced in English.

Bajan's nasalization patterns could have been reinforced by Iberian speakers.

Nalatalization and Affricates

Bajan Creole:

Tuesday → ['tʃuzde]

sugar → ['ʃugə]

Tendency to shift s/t before front vowels toward [ʃ]/[tʃ].

Portuguese:

tia → ['tʃiɐ]

cheio → ['ʃeju]

Portuguese routinely palatalizes before /i/ and /e/.

English has palatalization, but the breadth of palatalization in Bajan aligns more closely with Portuguese than with English.

Demonstrable and similar contractions

Bajan Creole:

In Bajan Creole 'Da' serves a different purpose than 'De', however I see Da as a construction of De and 'ah' creating 'Da' or the contracted, stressed 'dah'. 'Da is often used as a contraction, da + stress, which indicates location, stress, and expression in a specific manner. Othertimes, however, 'De' is contracted: De + y also becomes 'Dey' as in 'There' or 'They', make note of this contraction.

da (Unstressed “That”) **dah** (stressed “That”), daz/das (“that is”), dey (“there”).
S or Z = shortened es, is, iz.

Da + s\z = **that is**, instead of ‘The is’.

Da + h\ʌt = Stressed ‘That’

Bajan Creole: Da dey es mynes or daz yours?

Anglicized Bajan Translation: ‘That there is mine, or that’s yours?’

Iberianized Bajan Translation: ‘From that, there, is mine? Or ‘there’ is yours?’

Portuguese:

da(s)/do(s) from contraction of **de** + **article**.

‘**De** – Of, From’

de + **a** = **Da** – ‘Of\From The’ (Feminine)

de + **a** (Plural) = **Das**

De + **O** = **Do** — ‘Of\From The’ (Masculine)

De + **O** (Plural) = **Dos**

Examples: ‘Depois da tempestade vem a bonança’ – After the storm comes the calm.

‘Antes só do que mal-acompanhado’ – Better to be alone than in bad company.

Bajan’s dah/daz/das system shows functional overlap with Iberian demonstratives/articles, where contraction with an article shifts the linguistic meaning of commonly understood terms — not directly derived from English “that.”

Aspect / Habitual Markers

Bajan Creole: E duz guh church erre Sunduh (habitual marker duz).

Portuguese: Ele costuma ir à igreja todo domingo (habitual auxiliary costumar = “does usually”).

Parallel: Different words, but similar morphosyntactic strategy: auxiliary-like marker to indicate habitual aspect.

English doesn't mark habitual with a special particle.

Comparative analysis to Papiamentu:

When assessing Iberian roots in Barbadian Creole, it is helpful to compare with Papiamentu, the creole spoken in Aruba, Curaçao, and Bonaire. Papiamentu developed in the same seventeenth-century Caribbean contact zones, with Portuguese, Spanish, Sephardic Jews, Africans, and Dutch all shaping its structure.

Unlike Bajan, where Iberian traces have been minimized in scholarship, Papiamentu is widely acknowledged as having an Iberian base. It is the opinion of the author that this is because of the Empire to which the Barbadian Creole was formed, juxtaposed to other islands. The contrast reveals how the politics of colonial societies still affects modern social institutions and academic thought.

Pronouns

Papiamento: mi (I/me), bo (you), nos (we)

Portuguese/Spanish: me (mi), nós/nos (we), vos (you plural)

Bajan: me (“mi/I”), yuh (You, abstract), Wun-nuh (You, Plural)

Possession

Papiamento: *kasa di Juan* = John’s house

Portuguese: *casa de João*

Bajan: *de mann howse*

Definite Article / Function Word

Papiamento: di (of), e (the)

Portuguese: de / da / dos / das

Anglicized Bajan: de = the / Does = To do something (e.g. ‘Dat does pull’) / He (He)

Iberianized Bajan: de = Of (e.g., ‘Bring mi de ting’) / Dey = there (E.g. ‘Da dey’) / Duz = To do something (e.g. ‘Dah duz pull’) / E (He, or abstract for a person)

With the process of colonization and Creolization, English graves began appearing, and the rate at which they appeared increased throughout the centuries. Notably, the ‘last professing’ Jew of the Nidhe was not buried within the Nidhe Israel, nor was his grave in Portuguese, Spanish, or Hebrew; it was written in English. Thus, I make the argument that this process of Creolization did not fail to leave its own influence.

Barbadian Jews were ghettoized; they gathered within Speightstown, and Jew Street, now Swans Street. After the razing of the Speightstown Synagogue, the Speightstown Jews would once again be dispersed, some leaving the Island for good. The process of Portuguese Jewish influence on linguistic speech within colonial empires appeared in conjunction with the introduction of public education and the decline of integral communal functions, such as the Jewish School within the Nidhe Israel’s complex.

These institutions would have been sufficient to teach the language of the nation, considering this was how Portuguese Jews maintained their trade and mercantile networks, through their preservation of Portuguese, but this can be considered a bit speculative as the need to speak English might have been more pronounced even within Jewish communal life, given that it was resident to the British Empire, and some members leveraged these connections across diasporas.

Further, Education had oftentimes been deeply linked with structures that perpetuated religious control; the process of Iberian forms becoming anglicized was systematic and even advantageous for Jews within the

Colonial-Anglican British Empire. Respectability politics today exists not just in appearance or color, but in name.

For this reason, we often saw Sephardic Jews who would Christianize or Anglicize their names.

Most interestingly, this grouping is the ‘Barrow’ anglicization of the ‘Baruch Lousada’ Family, it is important to observe how the omission of middle names as a bureaucratic standard in anglophone discourse negatively impacted Iberian influenced communal record-keeping, up until the decline of the publicly practicing Jewish community, Barbadian Jews retained their own institutions for education, burial, and communal functions, although these institutions were only preserved for what would be considered white passing, halachically Jewish offspring.

Non-Jewish institutions had no reason to preserve integral details concerning lineages; many families would maintain their own genealogies, but these are not always entirely accurate. The intersection of Jewish law in the marginalization of the diasporic Afro-Portuguese identity is pronounced; modern descendants are considered no longer Jews, but I draw the question, does this mean I am also no longer Portuguese? Because my Jewish identity is directly linked to the progression of Portuguese ‘New Christian’ cultural norms.

How would Judeo-Portuguese have touched everyday Barbadian speech? In seventeenth-century Bridgetown and Speightstown, Sephardic merchants, dockworkers, servants, and neighbors interacted daily in markets, workshops, and households. In such contact zones, high-frequency items—articles/determiners and function words—are the most likely to diffuse. If an Iberian layer entered Bajan, we expect traces in the article system (e.g.,

de/da/das/do/dos in fixed phrases) and in prosody and vowel reduction patterns typical of European Portuguese. The following examples illustrate where Barbadian usage aligns with these predictions and how they differ from explanations based solely on English.

As noted in *Practice Portuguese* (n.d.), European Portuguese often reduces unstressed vowels—parallels found in Bajan contractions like *wuh* (“what”).

De higher de monkey climb, de more e show e tail. – The more you show off, the more you show people your faults.

Iberianized Bajan Interpretation: ‘**Of Higher From, Monkey Climb, of more he shows his tail**’ – **If read within the prepositional stacking of Old Galician Portuguese.**

Note about Anglicized Bajan: Anglicized Bajan keeps English pronunciations for things like ‘he’ however in Phonetic speech, ‘he’ is often shortened to ‘e’ such as in ‘**Yuh cayn talk tuh e’yuh**’ or ‘**E tink e bad, watch an see den**’

In Judaeo-Portuguese: Proverbial forms survive in Ladino and Judeo-Portuguese texts; prepositional stacking (*de ... os...*) is typical, and it appears in cultural phrases such as ‘**Todos los dedos de la mano no son unos**’ and ‘**O Livro De Magica**’, the latter being a famous **Rashi-Script Judaeo-Portuguese** book concerning medicine and other subjects.

Fun fact: The oldest known document is a treatise on the art of manuscript illumination dating from 1262, written in Portuguese with Hebrew characters –O livro de como se fazem as cores.

De devil duz find work fuh idle hands.

People with nothing to do are more likely to get into trouble.

Read through Iberianized Bajan: ‘From Devil is to find work for idle hands’

Portuguese: *O diabo encontra trabalho para mãos ociosas.*

Both: definite article + agent + verb + work/occupation structure.

In Bajan, *de* functions more like *de\da* than like English “the.”

Why was ‘duz’ translated to ‘is to’ here? Because ‘duz’ is a Barbadian verb meaning ‘to do’, the devil ‘to do’ ‘by finding’ work for idle hands. Duz is a verb which does not easily translate to english, anglicized bajan calls this term ‘does’ does appear, however anglicized bajan reads like: ‘**You does do da?**’

Which makes me think ‘does’ does not necessarily represent the english ‘do’ but a creolised term, **which sounds more like duhz**, which would give us ‘**Yuh duz do dah?**’

In this sentence there is no good translation for this interaction to english nor iberian, the closest substitute I could find, which made grammatical sense in english, would be ‘to’.

dah-fuh-lick-yuh

‘That is for ‘jokes’ you hear?’

un-it-do

‘Un of it’

- Undo it

Yuh cann’be en de church and de chapel too.

‘You cannot be in of Church and from Chapell, also’ – Read in Iberianized Bajan

‘You can’t be in more than one place at a time.’ — Colloquial meaning

Commentary, Creole

Creole languages have a curious status in linguistics, and at the same time, they often have very low prestige in the societies in which they are spoken. These two facts may be related, in part because they circle around notions such as “derived from” or “simplified” instead of “original.” –

Muysken, P. (2016, June 09). Creole Languages. Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Linguistics. Retrieved 20 Sep. 2025, from

<https://oxfordre.com/linguistics/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780199384655.001.0001/acrefore-9780199384655-e-6>

Conclusion

In conclusion, this essay has argued that the Barbadian Creole is diverse, and draws from many origin points and interpretations, dependent on community, location, ancestry, and origin. To acknowledge the multicultural, Sephardic-Portuguese and Jewish legacies of Barbados is to reclaim and recognise an important and vulnerable minority community within Barbados, as well as its contributions and exclusions from local scholarship.

Barbadian Creole is not simply broken English, but a language of exile, formed in diaspora in context to slavery, colonialism, antisemitism, and linguistic erasure. This essay discusses an additional layer of Barbadian identity, the intersection of Jewish, Portuguese, and Colonial identity. Sephardic Barbados left far more than wills, synagogue ruins, and tombstones, but a living, palpable contribution to the Barbadian Sociolinguistic footprint, even if generally neglected or understudied.

Creolization and linguistic adaptation remain an integral part of the Sephardic exilic experience. Barbadian Scholarship needs to more vigorously engage in Iberian dialogue and cultural threads to more adequately

understand its cultural identity; however, this remains true for all minority ethnic communities within Barbados, and global scholarship more widely.

Creole linguistics are not to be understood by any measure as butchered derivatives; the cognition of the colonized subject's language as inferior is a popular cultural narrative, however, with the advent of modern standards, so must the marginalised analyse themselves with as much dignity as those who considered themselves colonisers.

The Sephardic Barbadian story happens in context to other diasporas, such as the Irish, Asians, Africans, and other groupings of people from across Europe, the Middle East, and beyond.

Thus, to study Barbadian Creole is to study the linguistic development of communities historically entrenched within Barbadian systems, cultural debate, and global tensions. To study the contributions of our ancestors critically and interpretively is to insist that our words are not merely broken nor backward, but filled with memory, meaning, purpose, and inheritance. For each Barbadian, this may be for a different purpose—but for all Barbadians, our language stands as a testament to those who came before us, regardless of who they were, or where their sociolinguistic origins had been.

Recognizing Iberian survivals in Barbadian Creole not only reshapes our linguistic history but also reclaims a marginalized Sephardic legacy within Caribbean identity.

Glossary

Definitions, English

English is a language—originally the language of the people of England. Today, English is the main language of the United Kingdom, Ireland, the United States of America, Canada, Australia, New Zealand and more than fifty other countries. (Interestingly, until as recently as 2017 English was NOT the official language of the USA, although it had long been the official language of several US states.) – EnglishClub. (n.d.). What is English? Retrieved September 20, 2025, from <https://www.englishclub.com/what-is-english/>

Definitions, Portuguese History

The Portuguese language is an Indo-European language that is part of the Romance stem. As it is a Romance language, many Portuguese words have their roots in the Latin. The Romans brought this language to the Iberian Peninsula in 216BC, where it branched out over the centuries into many different languages, one of them being Old Portuguese.

Originally spoken in the medieval Kingdom of Galicia, Portuguese sailors in the Age of Exploration (the 16th century) travelled far and wide across the globe to colonize new areas of land. Many of these colonizations were successful and brought the Portuguese language to many new places, particularly Asia and Africa.

By the 16th century, it was a lingua franca for both of these areas, used in trade, commerce and government, as well as by many of the common people. Due to Portuguese settlers marrying many of the local people, as the Portuguese people also

brought with them the Catholic religion, the language spread rapidly at this time. Today, the Portuguese language is used all over the world, and as well as the direct Portuguese language itself, there are many Portuguese-based Creole languages that have developed, mostly in African and Asia.

The Portuguese language sounds very similar to the Spanish language. The grammatical structure of sentences, vocabulary, and syntax are all very much the same, and it is only accent and pronunciation that really make the difference between these two languages. Thus, there is a high level of intelligibility between these two languages, and someone who understands one language will be able to understand much of the other language.

Effective Language Learning. (n.d.). Portuguese language. Retrieved September 20, 2025, from <https://effectivelanguagelearning.com/language-guide/portuguese-language/>

Creolization Continued

“Three common features can usually be discerned among the diversity of uses found for the term: (1) Creolization involves a “double adaptation” as those arriving into a colonial territory adapt to the new environment and to each other. This is usually driven by those who have no prospect of returning to their home culture and who suffer the effects of racial domination. (2) Creolization has a “nativizing” trajectory according to which the cultural practices formed through the process of mixing and adaptation become a group’s “home” culture. (3) Creolization is incessant: it never arrives finally at a stable cultural compound but continually undergoes further intercultural exchange and transformation... A diversity of disciplines has found productive use for the concept, which has made for both rich interdisciplinary exchange and a complex and often contradictory array of different understandings.” — **Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Literature, Ben Etherington**

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